

DL 4.5 website as a platform

New EUPHRESKO website maintained on the EPPO server

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Welcome to Euphresco network

Euphresco is a network of organisations funding research projects and coordinating national research in the phytosanitary area. The overall goal of Euphresco is to support coordination and collaboration in the area of phytosanitary research, and to become a strong, long-term network of funders that fully incorporate existing and new members.

A leaflet about Euphresco can be found [HERE](#)

The rate of introduction and establishment of new plant pests has increased steadily over the last century as a result of expanding globalisation of trade, exacerbated by climate change. At the same time, European phytosanitary science capacity (taxonomy, classical plant pathology, etc.) has been eroding in the last decades, because they are no longer on the forefront of science priorities. This brought the plant health area to a state of emergency, as indicated by the [European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization's Madeira statement \(2004\)](#).

In Europe, many of the phytosanitary policies, regulations and underpinning technical recommendations are determined at regional level, while the research that supports them is mostly funded and carried out at the national level. Coordination of such national activities is then vital to reduce the impact of plant pests on the economy, the environment and the health of citizens at the level of each country but more generally at European and international level.

Latest news

Euphresco and SUMFOREST ERA-Net have initiated a cooperation around forestry. More information on SUMFOREST can be found [HERE](#)
2014-10-20 11:24

Euphresco and C-IPM ERA-Net have initiated a cooperation around the procedures leading to the funding of research projects. More information on C-IPM can be found [HERE](#)
2014-10-14 13:29

They talk about us on PLATFORM ERA-Net website! Follow the link [HERE](#)
2014-09-18 13:38

Euphresco was kindly invited to the "XIII Encuentro del Sistema de los INIA de Iberoamérica" in Guadalajara, Mexico, and good contacts were established for potential future collaborations with latin american countries. Muy bien!
2014-09-12 04:13

A new leaflet to explain the history of the Network and inform about current activities and the future is now available for [download](#)!
2014-09-05 10:03

The 2nd Euphresco Governing Board meeting will be held on September 24. The coordinator will present the tasks implemented since his arrival in June 2014 and the planning for the next twelve months.
2014-09-01 17:16